

NOTES

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Effects of Aquatic Toxic Trace Elements on the Quality of Foodfish

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THE recent discovery of relatively high levels of mercury in fish in North America has focused intense concern on numerous of other potentially toxic elements, such as mercury, copper, zinc, iron, manganese, magnesium, chromium, nickel, calcium, sodium, potassium and others which may be ubiquitous in ecosystems. Trace elements from anthropogenic activities and natural processes enter the marine environment. Such discharges are known to contain organic and inorganic micropollutants including toxic trace elements¹. The fish which live in polluted water may accumulate trace elements, some of which are toxic, from the water *via* their food chains. The fish feeding on small marine organisms, on algae, and on bottom sediments, readily accumulate trace elements, thus endangering human health².

Samples of saltwater fish from the Atlantic Coast of South Carolina were collected. The species composition of the collections generally reflects the

fish populations of the water sampled. Since nutritionally and recreationally fish constitute most important segment of the aquatic ecosystem, toxic elements in fish are obviously of great concern³.

Experimental

Source of materials: Samples of fish from the Atlantic Coast of South Carolina were collected during the summer 1978. The species composition of the collections generally reflects the fish populations of the water sampled. The fish collected were sheepshead (*Diplodus holbrooki*), sea bass (*Monrone saxatilis*), whiting (*Uopycis regius*), grouper (*Garrupa nigriral*), toad fish (*Opsanus tau*), dolphin (*Coryhaena hippurus*), cod (*Gadus morphua*), mullet (*Mugil cephalus*), Red snapper (*Lutianus aya*), silver snapper (*Lutianus grisens*), speckled trout (*Salventinus fontinalis*), and flounder (*Lophopsetta maculata*). The whole fresh fish were placed on ice in an ice-chest and given an identification number, the date of collection and the place of collection, and were then transported to the laboratory for weighing and storage. The whole fish were weighed and placed in plastic bags and stored in a freezer.

Wet digestion: Frozen fish samples were thawed and dissected. The pieces of edible muscle tissue, about (~10 g), were weighed accurately and placed in clean dry Erlenmeyer flasks which were closed with polyethylene stoppers. Sample flasks were digested in a constant temperature shaking water-bath at 58° until clear solution in nitric acid (reagent grade) was obtained (50-60 min). Sample flasks were removed from the bath and allowed to cool. The digests were diluted to 100 ml total volume with deionised water⁴.

Trace elements determination: The trace element contents of the digest were determined by flame atomic absorption spectrophotometer using a Perkin-Elmer 5000 and Perkin-Elmer 306 spectrophotometers². Determination of trace elements were measured as parts per million. Standard solution of each element was used in determination.

TABLE 1—TRACE ELEMENT LEVELS (ppm) IN SALTWATER FISH FROM THE ATLANTIC COAST OF SOUTH CAROLINA

Species	Whole body wt. g	Fe	Zn	Cu	Ni	Cr	Hg	Mn	Mg	Ca	Na	K
Sea bass	215.7	0.36	0.18	0.09	0.33	0.25	0.50	0.03	12.21	14.93	72.0	550
Sea bass	209.5	0.34	0.16	0.08	0.30	0.15	0.40	0.02	10.21	9.86	68.0	500
Whiting	167.2	0.34	0.32	0.08	0.10	0.15	0.50	0.03	11.99	23.90	79.5	500
Sheepshead	1 560.8	0.49	0.26	0.09	0.10	0.38	0.12	0.02	14.31	15.48	48.5	650
Mullet	446.3	0.72	0.16	0.05	0.20	0.40	0.15	0.12	14.42	30.10	75.5	600
Grouper	1 564.1	0.78	0.55	0.09	0.22	0.30	0.52	0.07	14.43	22.31	102.0	600
Grouper	744.5	0.63	0.25	0.04	0.20	0.10	0.12	0.04	10.18	12.68	59.5	500
Flounder	287.0	0.42	0.13	0.08	0.20	0.20	0.17	0.02	14.37	9.49	47.0	700
Dolphin fillet	363.6	0.74	0.24	0.13	0.15	0.20	0.20	0.11	9.48	10.82	30.0	200
Toad fish	611.2	0.57	0.19	0.10	0.25	0.15	0.21	0.05	10.40	6.99	24.5	700
Cod fillet	620.4	0.33	0.45	0.11	0.25	0.20	0.22	0.06	10.33	6.90	47.0	300
Red snapper	1 344.7	0.45	0.16	0.08	0.18	0.22	0.23	0.07	13.72	13.87	45.0	750
Red snapper	696.7	0.39	0.08	0.05	0.15	0.20	0.14	0.02	13.71	5.61	39.0	300
Silver snapper	230.0	0.48	0.19	0.10	0.15	0.45	0.32	0.02	15.03	8.90	57.0	700
Speckled trout	325.3	0.31	0.20	0.07	0.15	0.10	0.12	0.03	13.27	8.96	53.0	600

The trace elements determined were Fe, Cu, Zn, Mn, Mg, Ca, Hg, Cr, Ni, Na and K (Table 1). Mercury was determined by flameless atomic absorption spectrophotometry procedures outlined by Hatch and Ott⁵, and Uthe *et al.*⁶ as modified for use with a Perkin-Elmer Coleman MAS—50 mercury analyser.

Results and Discussion

The purpose of this study was to determine whether the fish from the Atlantic Coast of South Carolina have elevated concentrations of toxic trace elements and can become dangerous for human consumption. The fish species were analysed. Trace elements Fe, Cu, Zn, Mn, Mg, Ca, Hg, Cr, Ni, Na and K were determined. Those species for which fish of widely differing weights were analysed, larger fish had higher concentrations of trace elements than smaller fish. It seems that salt-water rather than fresh-water fish have more trace element contents. Variations in trace element levels found in this study probably reflect differences between species and differences in size, life histories,

dietary habits and the concentration in the marine environment.

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